

Numerical Simulation of Wind Flow Around High-Rise Buildings Having Different Aspect Ratios

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Abstract In the present era of massive urbanization there is an increase in the urban demand of structures, this coupled with the limited availability of land for construction is leading to the construction of high-rise slender structures. The design of these high-rise structures are primarily governed by the wind loads. With the advent of high computational capability and owing to the limitation of experimentation, the numerical simulation for wind flow around building has started gaining popularity. The numerical solution leads to much lower expenses for fixing of errors and gives a faster solution compared to experimentation. The current research work utilizes the open source CFD software Open FOAM and commercially available ANSYS software for numerical analysis. The research work presented in this article compares the effectiveness of the two CFD software for different aspect ratios of the high-rise buildings by comparing them with the available literature. RANS standard $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model is used for simulation purpose in both the software. In the simulation, constant inlet velocity of 10m/s is used. The post processed results are presented in the form of wind pressure contour plots and streamlines. The two software are found to be quite effective in prediction of the wind pressure contour plots and mean surface pressure coefficients (C_p) for different faces of the buildings. The maximum and minimum wind pressure coefficients ($C_{p, \max}$ and $C_{p, \min}$) are also found out for the different buildings. The two software display distinct advantages over each other in different aspects. The current study effectively utilizes stable RANS in foretelling the near-façade airflow patterns. The simulation results were able to predict the vortex formation and wake recirculation in the domain.

Keywords CFD, OpenFOAM, ANSYS, RANS equation, standard $k-\epsilon$ Turbulence Model.

Introduction

A Brief Background of Set-up

The use of CFD (computational fluid dynamics), as an alternate for wind tunnel testing in many wind applications has been made possible by the significant advancement in the computing resources in the recent years. However, the domain size, the meshing technique, and the boundary conditions — the three primary components of a CFD simulation—are the fundamental factors that determine the accuracy of simulation [1]. This research work discusses the fundamental theoretical underpinnings of using CFD simulations with constant input velocity and the suggests the techniques for adopting building domains and meshing for CFD models in ANSYS and OpenFOAM. When the wind pressure distribution, streamlines, and wind velocity for two square plan tall building measuring 10m ×10m in plan and having 10m in height and 20m in heights respectively are compared with the literature that is currently available, it is observed that OpenFOAM, an open-source CFD platform, performs as efficiently as ANSYS. This study illustrates the use of CFD simulation for flow visualisation around tall buildings. The quick development of computer technology makes it possible to solve rigorous mathematical equations involving complex flow conditions. All the Notations used in this research article is based on references [2] and [3].

A Brief Introduction of RANS standard $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model

Since the work involves exploration of RANS standard $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model that is adopted on the two software platforms (1). ANSYS commercial software and (2). OpenFOAM open-source free software. The findings of both the software platforms are compared and are validated with the available literatures. The two software platforms are found to perform equally well. Post-processing findings are presented in the Result and Discussion section later.

The two primary governing equations of fluid dynamics are related to mass conservation (1) and momentum (2). The (2) equation is also referred to as the fluid's Navier-Stokes equation.

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho u_i)}{\partial x_i} = 0 \tag{1}$$

$$\frac{\partial(\rho u_i)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho u_i u_j)}{\partial x_j} = -\frac{\partial P}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\mu \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \right] \tag{2}$$

Instantaneous and Mean Velocity

- The instantaneous velocity (U), the measured velocity in the real (turbulent) fluid flow at a specific place (typical), would resemble this in Fig.1
- At any instantaneous time: $U = \bar{U} + u'$

Figure 1 Instantaneous and Mean Velocity [2]

- The fluctuating velocity time average needs to be zero ($\overline{u'} = 0$)
- $\overline{u'}$'s RMS is not necessarily zero ($\overline{u'^2} \neq 0$)
- In a turbulent flow, the kinetic energy per unit mass of the turbulent fluctuations, u_i' is known as the turbulence kinetic energy, k . It is given by

$$k = \frac{1}{2} \overline{u'_i u'_i} = \frac{1}{2} [\overline{u'^2_x} + \overline{u'^2_y} + \overline{u'^2_z}] = \frac{3}{2} [\overline{u'^2}]$$

Since work implemented RANS (Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes), Averaged velocity is used.

Time averaging

$$\bar{f} = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T f(x_i, t) dt \tag{3}$$

Instantaneous field of pressure and velocity as sum of mean and fluctuating component

- $p = \bar{p} + p'$
- $u_i = \bar{u}_i + u'_i$

By averaging the mass conservation and Navier-Stokes equations (1) and (2), averaged mass conservation equation and Averaged Navier-Stokes equation is obtained (4) and (5).

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial (\rho \bar{u}_i)}{\partial x_i} = 0 \tag{4}$$

$$\frac{\partial (\rho \bar{u}_i)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial (\rho \bar{u}_i \bar{u}_j)}{\partial x_j} = -\frac{\partial P}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\mu \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} - \frac{2}{3} \delta_{ij} \frac{\partial u_m}{\partial x_m} \right) \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(-\rho \overline{u'_i u'_j} \right) \tag{5}$$

Reynolds stress tensor, Rij

RANS standard $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model transport equation in OpenFOAM and ANSYS Fluent

All the basic mathematical partial differential equation used in ANSYS Fluent and OpenFoam is presented in table 1.

Literature Review

Weerasuriya, A. U. (2013, July 30): this work involves ABL simulation using CFD. It recommended methods for creating domains and meshes for CFD models. The study compared findings of wind tunnel tests with the pressure distribution simulations from CFD on 112m tall buildings [1]. Mukherjee, S. et al. (2014): The primary focus of the research is examination of the pressure exerted on the various faces of a tall building with a 'Y' plan shape. With a mean wind velocity of 10 m/s, the flow condition is consistent with terrain type II of IS:875 (Part 3) - 1987[8]. Chauhan, B.S. et al. (2020): The investigation of interference's impact on various tall building components with a rectangular cross-sectional shape. The two building models are arranged in an L-shape in plan to simulate real-life scenarios. By varying the height of the interfering buildings with respect to the principal building, findings are recorded [7]. Wijesooriya, K. et al. (2021): The research input pertains to the numerical validation of an efficient uncoupled fluid-structure interaction (FSI) method that is employed in assessing the structural reactions of extremely tall structures. An innovative method is used to translate wind-induced pressures into nodal time history loads that execute an implicit modal analysis and extract the time history response of the structure [6]. Yuan, Y. et al. (2022): This study focuses on developing a set of inflow boundary conditions based on RANS simulations with a focus on horizontal uniformity in particular, to resemble the twisted wind field. Additionally, the study aims to predict the aerodynamic forces acting on a squared tall building using these simulated twisted winds. The study used $k-\omega$ SST model [5]. Zaki, A. et al. (2023): The article focuses on the ventilation flows in a structure that has building arrays surrounding a windcatcher. Two forms of surrounding building arrangements, inline and staggered, were studied to represent different suburban morphologies. According to the findings, the maximum ventilation rate reductions for inline and staggered arrays, respectively, were 30% and 42% when compared to an isolated building example [4].

Table 1 standard k-ε turbulence model transport equation in OpenFOAM and ANSYS Fluent

OpenFOAM [3]	ANSYS Fluent [2]
<p>Model equation for Turbulence kinetic energy, k,</p> $\frac{D}{Dt}(\rho k) = \nabla \cdot (\rho D_k \nabla k) + P - \rho \epsilon \quad (6)$ <p>OpenFOAM implementation of Turbulence kinetic energy, k obtained from (Eq. 6 (i))</p> $\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\alpha \rho k) + \nabla \cdot (\alpha \rho u k) - \nabla^2(\alpha \rho D_k k) = \alpha \rho G - \left(\frac{2}{3} \alpha \rho \nabla \cdot u k\right) - \alpha \rho \frac{\epsilon}{k} k + S_k + S_{fvOptions} \quad (6(i))$ <p>S_k= internal source term pertaining to k $S_{fvOptions}$=Source term introduced by $S_{fvOptions}$ for k</p>	<p>Turbulence kinetic energy, k obtained from (Eq. 9) transport equation</p> $\frac{\partial(\rho k)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho k u_i)}{\partial x_i} = \left[\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_k} \right) \left(\frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \right) \right] + G_k + G_b - \rho \epsilon - Y_M + S_k \quad (9)$ <p>The fluctuation dilatation in compressible turbulence's contribution to the total dissipation rate is denoted by Y_M. a is speed of sound ($a = \sqrt{\gamma RT}$) $Y_M = 2\rho \epsilon M_t^2$ Where M_t is turbulent Mach Number calculated by $M_t = \sqrt{\frac{k}{a^2}}$</p>
<p>Turbulence kinetic energy dissipation rate, ϵ obtained from (Eq. 7) transport equation</p> $\frac{D}{Dt}(\rho \epsilon) = \nabla \cdot (\rho D_\epsilon \nabla \epsilon) + \frac{C_1 \epsilon}{k} \left(P + C_3 \frac{2}{3} k \nabla \cdot u \right) - C_2 \rho \frac{\epsilon^2}{k} \quad (7)$ <p>OpenFOAM implementation of Turbulence kinetic energy dissipation rate, ϵ obtained from (Eq. 7(i))</p> $\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\alpha \rho \epsilon) + \nabla \cdot (\alpha \rho u \epsilon) - \nabla^2(\alpha \rho D_\epsilon \epsilon) = C_1 \alpha \rho G \frac{\epsilon}{k} - \left(\frac{2}{3} C_1 - C_{3,RDT} \right) \alpha \rho \nabla \cdot u \epsilon - C_2 \alpha \rho \frac{\epsilon}{k} \epsilon + S_\epsilon + S_{fvOptions} \quad (7(i))$ <p>α= The specified phase's phase fraction G=Anisotropic component of the Reynolds-stress tensor causes turbulent kinetic energy production at a turbulent rate (m^2/s^3). D_k is diffusivity for k, D_ϵ is diffusivity for ϵ C_1, C_2, C_μ and $C_{3,RDT}$(Rapid-distortion theory compression term coefficient) are model coefficients</p>	<p>Turbulence kinetic energy dissipation rate, ϵ obtained from (Eq. 10) transport equation</p> $\frac{\partial(\rho \epsilon)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho \epsilon u_i)}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_\epsilon} \right) \left(\frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial x_j} \right) \right] + c_{1\epsilon} \frac{\epsilon}{k} [G_k + c_{3\epsilon} G_b] - c_{2\epsilon} \rho \frac{\epsilon^2}{k} + S_\epsilon \quad (10)$ <p>The mean velocity gradients produced turbulent kinetic energy is denoted by G_k. G_k calculated by $G_k = -\rho \bar{u}_i \bar{u}_j \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i}$ Turbulent viscosity μ_t obtained from (Eq. 11) $\mu_t = C_\mu \rho \frac{k^2}{\epsilon} \quad (11)$ model constants have following default values $C_{1\epsilon}=1.44$, $C_{2\epsilon}=1.92$, $C_\mu=0.09$, $\sigma_k=1.0$, $\sigma_\epsilon=1.3$ and $c_{3\epsilon} = \tanh \left \frac{v}{u} \right$ For buoyant shear layers perpendicular to the gravitational vector $c_{3\epsilon}$ will equal 0. S_k and S_ϵ are user defined source terms.</p>

Instead of being kept in a single case file, OpenFOAM data is kept as a collection of files inside a case directory. The necessary data can be found in the three directories shown in Fig. 2 under the appropriately descriptive name assigned to the case directory.

Figure 2 OpenFoam case directories

Methodology

Modelling of Isolated Assumed Prototype Buildings

CFD simulation is done on two software platforms namely ANSYS Fluent and OpenFOAM. Main components of the CFD are same for both platforms namely 1. Computational Domain 2. Meshing methodology 3. Boundary Conditions.

Computational Domain

For the purpose of numerical simulation, the research assumes prototype buildings (1:5 scale) of square plan with dimensions 10m x 10m in plan and 10m height and 20m heights. The domain should be sufficiently large so as to prevent fluid streams from reflecting and creating unnatural pressure fields around the building model. From the study of literature, it can be found that from the obstruction present in the wind flow field, the lateral and top distance of the domain boundary should be at least 5H from obstruction, where H is the height of the obstruction (building). For the case under consideration 5H is taken as the distance of the obstruction (building) from the inlet boundary. For outflow boundary distance, it should be at least 10H from outer edge of the building (obstruction), this distance is taken as 15H for the case under consideration. All distances are measured from the respective outer edges of the building (Fig. 3) and all the boundary conditions used are shown in Fig.4. Modelling of assumed prototype buildings for ANSYS Fluent is done on ANSYS Design Modeler and for OpenFoam modelling is done on FreeCAD is presented in Fig.5.

Figure 3 Computational Domain Size

Figure 4 Modelling in ANSYS Design Modeler

Figure 5 Modelling in FREECAD for OpenFoam

Methodology

Meshing methodology Several meshing techniques were tried i.e. tetrahedral mesh (Fig. 6) by automatic method with refinement close to the building, with inflation layers (Fig. 7), hexa-dominant mesh (Fig. 8) with inflation layers so as to accurately capture the wind velocity/pressure variation in ANSYS Fluent. Polyhedral type mesh is also used by converting tetrahedral mesh through fluent solver[2] and results were noted. For both the software platforms RANS steady analysis has been carried out. In OpenFoam blockMesh and snappyHexMesh command is used for meshing and refining the object. snappyHexMesh (Fig. 9) is providing hexahedral mesh with more accurate results. Even tetrahedral creation from Salome (Fig.10) or other type mesh can also be used in OpenFoam by importing from third party software like Salome open-source software, ANSYS Fluent meshing can be imported to OpenFoam by using command ideasUnvToFoam Mesh_Name.unv and fluentMeshToFoam Mesh_Name.msh respectively. However, hexahedral meshing in ANSYS provided with refinement or inflation layers close to the building and snappyHexMesh were found to be the most efficient form for both the software platforms for the case under consideration. As hexahedral meshes are economic with the number of elements because the same degree of freedom (or for 8 nodes) for one hexahedron corresponds to six Tetrahedra. As In this research, simple cubical geometries are present, hexahedron elements fit correctly. Faces present in prototype building are expressed in Fig. 11 as per Indian Standard IS875(part-3):2015, windward face is A, leeward face is B and side faces are face C and D respectively.

Figure 6 Tetrahedral Mesh with refinement in ANSYS

Figure 7 Tetrahedral Mesh with inflation Layers in ANSYS

Figure 8 Hexa Dominant Mesh in ANSYS with refinement

Figure 9 snappyHexMesh for OpenFoam

Figure 10 Tetrahedral mesh for OpenFoam (Salome)

Figure 11 Face description of assumed prototype buildings

Boundary Conditions for both the software platforms

- inlet = constant velocity inlet (10m/s)
- outlet=pressure outlet
- Top, both sides= symmetry (Free slip wall)
- Ground= No slip wall
- Building = No slip wall

Results and Discussions

Analysis

All the calculation and analysis has been carried out for standard *k-ε* turbulence viscous model for steady case in both software platforms i.e. ANSYS and OpenFoam and the results have been compared for constant inlet velocity of 10m/s. Drag Force and Drag Coefficient on buildings are calculated from both the software platforms and compared with Indian standard IS875(part-3):2015.

$$\text{Drag Force } (F_D) = \text{Static Wind Pressure } (p) \times \text{Normal surface area}$$

$$\text{Drag Coefficient } (C_d) = \frac{F_D}{\frac{1}{2} \rho A V^2}$$

where ρ , A and V are the air density, reference area and Free stream velocity respectively.

Coefficient of pressure C_p is calculated on all the Faces of buildings on both the softwares at various positions $h/H=0,0.005,0.01,0.05,0.1,0.15,0.20, \dots, 0.90,0.95,0.99,0.995$ and 1 as follows:

$$C_p = \frac{P - P_\infty}{\frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho V^2}$$

Where h and H are height measured from ground and total height respectively. Average C_p values for different faces are calculated by average pressure area methods for both the softwares and later these values are validated with IS875(part-3):2015. Some of the comparisons from this study are presented in the form of XY plots from Figs. 12 to 25. The X axis of these plots represent the position (m), from 0-10m position defines the C_p variation for face A, similarly 10-20m defines face C, 20-30m defines face B and 30-40m defines face D respectively. Fig. 24 and Fig. 25 shows the C_p at windward face of vertical center line i.e. C_p is aligned through x-axis.

Figure 12 Comparison of C_p at $h/H=0$ for 10m height building or aspect ratios $h/w=1, l/w=1$

Figure 13 Comparison of C_p at $h/H=0$ for 20m height building or aspect ratios $h/w=2, l/w=1$

Figure 14 Comparison of C_p at $h/H=0.1$ for 10m height building or aspect ratios $h/w=1, l/w=1$

Figure 15 Comparison of C_p at $h/H=0.1$ for 20m height building or aspect ratios $h/w=2, l/w=1$

Figure 16 Comparison of C_p at $h/H=0.25$ for 10m height building or aspect ratios $h/w=1, l/w=1$

Figure 17 Comparison of C_p at $h/H=0.25$ for 20m height building or aspect ratios $h/w=2, l/w=1$

Figure 18 Comparison of C_p at $h/H=0.5$ for 10m height building or aspect ratios $h/w=1, l/w=1$

Figure 19 Comparison of C_p at $h/H=0.50$ for 20m height building or aspect ratios $h/w=2, l/w=1$

Figure 20 Comparison of C_p at $h/H=0.75$ for 10m height building or aspect ratios $h/w=1, l/w=1$

Figure 21 Comparison of C_p at $h/H=0.75$ for 20m height building or aspect ratios $h/w=2, l/w=1$

Figure 22 Comparison of C_p at $h/H=0.90$ for 10m height building or aspect ratios $h/w=1, l/w=1$

Figure 23 Comparison of C_p at $h/H=0.90$ for 20m height building or aspect ratios $h/w=2, l/w=1$

Figure 24 Comparison of C_p on vertical line at windward face at center for 10m height building or aspect ratios $h/w=1, l/w=1$

Figure 25 Comparison of C_p on vertical line at windward face at center for 20m height building or aspect ratios $h/w=2, l/w=1$

For the both the square plan buildings of 10m height and 20m height, the value of Drag Force are **6829.1113N** and **13992.182N** respectively and the value of Drag coefficients are **1.138** and **1.166** in ANSYS Fluent $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model. For the both the square plan buildings of 10m height and 20m height, the value of Drag Force are **6692.87N** and **13952.10N** respectively and the value of Drag coefficients are **1.1154** and **1.1626** in OpenFoam $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model. Fig. 26 is showing the comparison of C_d and C_p obtained from both the softwares with Indian Standard IS875(part-3):2015^[9]. The value of C_p on different faces at A, B, C and D at 0° for IS875(part-3):2015^[9] is extracted from Table 5 and Clause 7.3.3.1of code for $\frac{1}{2} < \frac{h}{w} \leq \frac{3}{2}$ and $1 \leq \frac{l}{w} \leq \frac{3}{2}$ for 10m height building since this building has $h/w=1$ and $l/w=1$. The value of C_p on different faces at A, B, C and D at 0° for IS875(part-3):2015^[9] is extracted from Table 5 and Clause 7.3.3.1of code for $\frac{3}{2} < \frac{h}{w} < 6$ and $1 < \frac{l}{w} \leq \frac{3}{2}$ for 20m height building since this building has $h/w=2$ and $l/w=1$. The value of force coefficient is calculated from Fig.4 and clause 7.4.2.1 of code^[9].

Comparison of C_d and C_p obtained from ANSYS Fluent and OpenFoam for both the buildings of 10m and 20m heights with Indian Standard IS:875(part-3)-2015

Force coefficients/ Drag Coefficient (C_f) are obtained from the graph of Fig. 4 of IS875(part-3):2015^[9] shown in Fig. 27 of this research.

Figure 27 Force coefficients as per IS875(part-3):2015

Post-Processing of results

For visualization of Velocity streamlines, one XZ plane is inserted on D face for both software platforms shown in Fig. 28 and Fig. 31 (for 10m height building) and in Fig. 34 and Fig. 37 (for 20m height building). Streamlines patterns are shown in Fig. 29 and Fig. 32 (for 10m height building) and in Fig. 35 and Fig. 38 (for 20m height building). Pressure contours on windward face of buildings of 10m height are shown in Fig. 30 and Fig. 33 (for 10m height building) and in Fig. 36 and Fig. 39 (for 20m height building). Same velocity flow and pressure contours plot patterns are obtained on both the software platforms.

Future Research Scope

In this research article, Inlet Constant velocity is assumed 10m/s for the turbulence airflow around tall buildings of different aspect ratios. Different velocity profile may be used for analysis. In this article only Inlet velocity is assumed for 0° Angle of Attack (AOA). In IS875(part-3):2015 only C_p value is given for 0° and 90° only. Other AOA can also be used for analysis purposes in OpenFOAM as very less study is available for OpenFOAM.

Conclusions

Major derived conclusions from the obtained results are:

1. From ANSYS Fluent platform, For the both the square plan buildings of 10m height and 20m height, the value of Drag Force are **6829.1113N** and **13992.182N** respectively and the value of Drag coefficients are **1.138** and **1.166** in ANSYS Fluent $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model. Indian standard Code IS875(part-3):2015 has Drag coefficient **1.26** and **1.30** respectively for 10m and 20m height buildings. Errors are 9.68% and 10.30% are respectively which are within permissible limits.
2. From OpenFoam platform, For the both the square plan buildings of 10m height and 20m height, the value of Drag Force are **6692.87N** and **13952.10N** respectively and the value of Drag coefficients are **1.1154** and **1.1626** in OpenFoam $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model Indian standard Code IS875(part-3):2015 has Drag coefficient **1.26** and **1.30** respectively for 10m and 20m height buildings. Errors are 11.47% and 10.56% are respectively which are within permissible limits. From the results obtained for the two buildings, it can be observed that the Drag Force got approximately doubled by increasing the height twice for the same plan area.
3. As per code IS:875(part-3)-2015, The total C_p value for across buildings faces namely windward and leeward faces should be $0.7+(0.25) = 0.95$ for 10m height building and $0.8+0.25=1.05$ for 20m height building respectively. OpenFoam gives total across C_p values $0.61+(0.36) = 0.97$ for 10m height building and $0.605+0.42=1.025$ for 20m height building, which have 2.105% and 2.38% errors respectively. ANSYS Fluent gives total across C_p values are $0.6260+(0.30799) = 0.93$ for 10m height building and $0.66+0.37=1.03$ for 20m height building respectively, which have 2.105% and 1.904% errors respectively values are within permissible limits for both the software.
4. From the obtained results It has been recorded that side faces have better results in OpenFoam than ANSYS Fluent for $k-\epsilon$ steady turbulence model.
5. Maximum Positive coefficient of pressure $C_{p, Max}$ is 1.016 in OpenFoam and 1.046 in ANSYS Fluent respectively at windward face/Face A on both the software platforms for 10m height building. While for 20m height building $C_{p, Max}$ is found to be 0.98 in OpenFoam and 0.9805 in ANSYS Fluent respectively again on windward face/Face A in both the softwares.
6. Maximum Negative coefficient of pressure $C_{p, Min}$ is found to be -0.833 in OpenFoam and -0.737 in ANSYS Fluent respectively on side faces C/D in both the software platforms for 10m height building. While for 20m height building $C_{p, Min}$ is found to be -0.9 in OpenFoam and -0.86 in ANSYS Fluent respectively again on side faces C/D in both the softwares.
7. OpenFoam software platform performs equally well as ANSYS Fluent as validated with the literature.

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